

Correlation of Viscous Flow in Electrolyte Solutions Relative to the Glassy State at the Isotherm Temperature

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Vogel-Tammann-Fulcher (VTF) equation¹ is a useful description of the effect of temperature on the viscosity of liquids in the neighbourhood of glassy region. A theoretical basis for VTF equation was later provided in the framework of the free volume model of liquids by Turnbull and Cohen². By considering that the configurational entropy vanishes at the ideal glass transition temperature (T_0), Gibbs and coworkers³ could recover a VTF type of equation which adequately describes viscosity (η) behaviour of liquids at low temperature,

$$\frac{1}{\eta} = A \exp \left[-\frac{k_0}{T-T_0} \right] \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), η is the viscosity of the liquid at temperature T (K), A and k_0 are constants and T_0 is the ideal glass transition temperature. Equation (1) was adopted for electrolyte solutions by Angell^{4,5},

$$\frac{1}{\eta} = A \exp \left[-\frac{k'}{N_0-N} \right] \quad (2)$$

by assuming that the ideal glass transition temperature $T_0(N)$ is linearly dependent on electrolyte concentration, N equivalents per litre,

$$T_0(N) = T_0 + pN \quad (3)$$

$$T = T_0 + pN_0 \quad (4)$$

p being a constant dependent on solute-solvent interaction. As the linearity of plot of $\ln 1/\eta$ vs $1/(N_0-N)$ extends to zero salt concentration, it was suggested that $\eta \rightarrow \eta_0$, the viscosity of the pure solvent, as $N \rightarrow 0$. Introducing this limiting condition, it was possible to recast the Angell's equation in the form⁶,

$$\ln \eta_{rel} = \frac{k' N}{N_0(N_0-N)} \quad (5)$$

In equations (2)–(5), T_0 is the ideal glass transition temperature of pure solvent and N_0 the hypothetical concentration at which the solution would pass into the glassy state at the temperature T . This is the temperature at which the measured values of η_{rel} in equation (5) refer. Further,

$$k' = k_0/p$$

It is supposed that k' is independent of composition and involves solute-solvent as well as solvent-solvent interaction.

It was seen earlier^{7,8} that the Jones-Dole B -coefficient is

$$B = f \frac{k}{N_0^2} \quad (6)$$

where the factor f is introduced so as to obtain B in the usual unit of $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ and it is equal to 2 for bivalent metal nitrates and 3 for rare earth chlorides. Insertion of B into equation (4) yields an equation of viscosity⁸,

$$\ln \eta_{rel} = \frac{BN_0 N}{N_0 - N} \quad (7)$$

in one unknown parameter N_0 . Extensive tables of B are available in the literature⁹.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\ln \eta_{rel}$ vs $N/(N_0-N)$ for bivalent metal nitrates in aqueous solution at 25° : (O) $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (\square) $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (Δ) $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (\bullet) $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (\blacksquare) $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (\blacktriangle) $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (\bullet) $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (\blacklozenge) $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (based on the experimental results of Doan and Sangster¹⁰).

Discussion and correlation of viscous flow :

In absence of any direct experimental measurement of N_0 , we seek to obtain correlation of viscous flow in electrolyte solutions with the parameters N_0 and B of equation (7). For this purpose we have chosen to analyse the available experimental results of viscosity measurements in two series of electrolytes in aqueous solutions : (i) 2 : 1 metal nitrates¹⁰ and (ii) rare-earth chlorides¹¹. The viscosity of bivalent metal nitrates in aqueous solution covers the range from 0.1 M to as high as 5.0 M and those of rare earth chlorides from 0.01 to 3.5 M . Fig. 1 shows the plot of $\ln \eta_{rel}$ vs $N/(N_0-N)$ of a number of 2 : 1 metal nitrates in aqueous solutions. The values of η_{rel} at various concentrations are those determined by Doan and Sangster¹⁰. It is seen that with suitable choice of N_0 , the relevant plot for each of these electrolytes is a straight-line passing through the origin. The values of N_0 required to linearise equation (5) is obtained by a trial method described earlier¹² (Table 1). The fact that the viscosity of bivalent metal nitrates in aqueous solutions follows equation (5) gives credence to the essential validity of equations (3) and (4). Angell⁵ observed that the experimental glass transition temperature (T_g) is generally raised in a linear manner for the nitrates and rare earth chlorides in aqueous solution. In support of equation (3) we may also cite the experimental evidence¹³ for hydrogen halides and lithium chloride in aqueous solution in restricted range of concentration. Table 1 shows the values of fk'/N_0^2 and these are compared with the Jones-Dole B -coefficient reported by Breslau and Miller¹⁴. The agreement excepting $Pb(NO_3)_2$ and $Fe(NO_3)_2$ are reasonably fair.

TABLE 1—VALUES^a OF VISCOSITY PARAMETERS FOR BIVALENT METAL NITRATES IN AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Salt	N_0 eq/dm ³	fk'/N_0^2	B (lit.) ^b	BN_0^c
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	21.6	0.297	0.293	3.21
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	13.6	0.239	0.170	2.88
Pb(NO ₃) ₂	10.8	0.195	0.141	1.05
Fe(NO ₃) ₂	33.6	0.676	0.324	11.36
Cu(NO ₃) ₂	20.9	0.366	0.293	3.83
Cd(NO ₃) ₂	22.5	0.319	0.228	3.59
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	26.6	0.312	0.378	4.15
Ni(NO ₃) ₂	21.7	0.312	0.292	3.39

^aThe values of fk'/N_0^2 and N_0 are based on the experimental values of viscosity reported in Ref. 10. ^bRef 14, Jones-Dole coefficient. ^cValues of B required for computing BN_0 are those given in column 4.

For rare earth chlorides in aqueous solution, the product BN_0 was interpreted¹⁵ as a measure of the number of flow units in the cooperatively rearranging domain in the glassy state at the isotherm temperature T . The BN_0 was found to centre around two ranges 4.75–5.14 and 6.15–6.54 and was believed¹⁵ to be a characteristic property of viscous flow in electrolyte solution. We have, therefore, calculated the

values of BN_0 for bivalent metal nitrates as well. It is seen in Table 1 that the values of BN_0 for the nitrates range around 2.9–4.2 excepting $Pb(NO_3)_2$ and $Fe(NO_3)_2$.

Fig. 2 shows the plots of $\ln \eta_{rel}/BN_0$ against N/N_0 for the bivalent metal nitrates and for the rare earth chlorides

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln \eta_{rel}/BN_0$ vs N/N_0 for bivalent metal nitrates and rare earth chlorides in aqueous solution at 25° : Curve-I (▲) Zn(NO₃)₂, (■) Cd(NO₃)₂, (●) Cu(NO₃)₂, (△) Fe(NO₃)₂, (⊗) Pb(NO₃)₂, (▲) Sr(NO₃)₂, (▣) Ni(NO₃)₂ and (●) Mg(NO₃)₂; Curve-II (○) ErCl₃, (△) DyCl₃, (□) HoCl₃, (○) TbCl₃, (⊞) SmCl₃, (▲) NdCl₃ and (▧) LaCl₃ (based on the experimental results of Doan and Sangster¹⁰ and Spedding and Pikal¹¹).

in aqueous solution. The relevant values of η_{rel} required for the plot are those determined by Doan and Sangster¹⁰ and Spedding and Pikal¹¹. It is seen that a single curve can be drawn through all the rare earth chlorides (curve-II) and another single curve goes through all the nitrates (curve-I). Thus a related series of electrolytes with similar charge type and having a common anion, such as bivalent metal nitrates or the rare earth chlorides, shows a kind of corresponding state behaviour. This is a previously unrecognised correlation, which we obtain by using BN_0 as a scaling factor. That this should be so, follows from equation (7),

$$\ln \eta_{rel}/BN_0 = \frac{N/N_0}{1-N/N_0} \quad (8)$$

This striking correlation suggests that N_0 is not just a parameter but a quantity of important physical significance.

Identification of Jones-Dole B -coefficient with fk'/N_0^2 extends the scope of the existing interpretation of B -coeffi-

cient. It is commonly held that the B -coefficient is a measure of solute (ion)-solvent interaction. According to our analysis, as $k' = k^0/p$, the B -coefficient involves solute-solvent as well as solvent-solvent interactions. The viscosity increase is, therefore, due to two factors, (i) ion (solute)-solvent interaction and (ii) interaction of solvent perturbation flow. The B -coefficient is thus dependent on both the factors. In 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 electrolyte solution it is likely that the factor (i) i.e. solute-solvent interaction will predominate and the B -coefficient should be less than 1. Reference to Table 1, the B -coefficient for the bivalent metal nitrates and rare earth chlorides in aqueous solutions are indeed less than 1. The literature values¹⁶ of B -coefficient for the alkali metal halides also corroborate this observation. On the other hand, the relatively large values of B -coefficient¹⁷ for tetrabutylammonium bromide ($B = 1.35$) in water suggests that the factor (ii), i.e. interaction of solvent perturbation flow predominates rather than ion-solvent interaction. This is quite plausible in view of low charge density on the large cations.

We may conclude that the idea of a hypothetical solution of concentration, N_0 equivalent per litre at the isotherm temperature T is a useful concept which leads to correlation suggesting a kind of corresponding behaviour of viscous flow in electrolyte solutions, at least for the bivalent metal nitrates and rare earth chlorides.

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